

**NIGERIA'S FOREIGN POLICY SINCE RETURN OF
DEMOCRACY WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE
TO PRESIDENT OLUSEGUN OBASANJO'S
ADMINISTRATION, 1999 -2007**

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Abstract

Foreign policy is a contraction of domestic policies intended to promote and protect national interest as states engaged one after another for relevance and voice in the international system. Nigerian foreign policy over the years has been grossly sabotaged and undermined by image crisis both internally and externally. With the return of democracy in 1999, the protection of our national interest has remained the permanent focus of our foreign policy. Against this background, therefore, the paper examines the Nigerian foreign policy under President Obasanjo's administration from 1999 to 2007. However, the paper employs the use of historical research method whereby secondary data from relevant sources were analyzed and provided a clear picture of an attitudinal posture of the foreign policy. It suggests that, Nigeria should redirect its diplomatic strategy to reflect the demands of a globalizing world. In the final analysis, the paper concludes that Nigeria's foreign policy under Obasanjo's administration to some extent improved Nigeria's popularity and prestige among the comity of nations.

Keywords: Foreign Policy, Diplomacy, National interest and Nigeria.

1.1 Introduction:

The foreign policy of a country does not just emerge, but to a considerable extent it is determined by its domestic structure which involves the various constituent elements in the political system like the governments, the political parties, pressure groups, the civil service the political bureaucratic elites, public opinion and the press. All these operate within the democratic process provided by the constitution to exert direct or indirect influence in the shaping of its foreign policy. "Foreign policy aimed at getting other countries to appreciate and if possible, endorse one's own view points and objectives in the international system". (Gambari, 1996) "the ultimate objective of any nation's foreign policy is the pursuit and protection of its national interest" (Garba, J. 1989).

Therefore, the broad goals and objective of Nigeria's' foreign policy since independence, have remained constant and although the style and conduct have changed, there have been no profound changes in the content of substance of the foreign policy. It is observed that, the trends of Nigeria's foreign policy since independence in 1960 to date emanate from the basic formulation of the principles, aims and objectives of the Balewa's era. The basic objective of each successive administration from their varying perspectives, have sought to identify the ultimate aim and objective of Nigeria in relationship with the international system.

Olatunde (1982) also observed that, some salient and apparently contradictory features have marked Nigerian's external relation since its independence in 1960. Hence despite the several changes in regime and leadership, there has been an amazing continuity in the substance of Nigerian's foreign policy. However, this paper presentation intends to examine the Nigerian foreign policy under Olusegun Obasanjo's administration from 1999 to 2007. Thus, the paper is divided into sections, section one covers introduction, section two handles conceptual clarification, section three deals with theoretical framework, section four covers the brief biography of Olusegun Obasanjo and the assessment of Nigeria's foreign policy under Obasanjo's administration, while section five covers summary and conclusion.

2. Conceptual Clarification

2.1 Policy: Policy as a concept has far reaching meaning depending on the context or sphere it is being used. According to Deutsch Karl (1972) policy is an explicit set of future decision more nearly predictable and consistent i.e. policy stand as interest put in order to achieve certain result. Holsti K.J (19770 Define policies as goals, set precedence or laid down courses of actions and actions taken to implement these decisions i.e. the concept of policy stands as a course of action and what is been done to ensure or achieve this course of action.

2.2 Foreign Policy

Foreign policy is a system of action of one government or state towards another. Foreign policy is a dynamic process of interaction between the changing domestic demands, support and the changing external circumstances. Lanche C. (1963) define foreign policy as the course of actions and the decision relating to them, that a state undertakes in its relations with other in order to attain its national objectives and advance national interests. It is also referring to the general principles by which a state governs its reaction to the international environment in other words it is a reaction to external stimuli and situations requiring response.

Form these definitions, the content and direction of the foreign policy of states are necessarily shaped by three distinctive factors. The first is the political environment in which the state operates. The second is the specific reactions of other state to policies. The third is the state's capabilities to undertake action in the form of an initiative or in response to external stimuli. (Ayuba, 2000) Thus, the role foreign policy lies within the segment of general tendency and principles that underlies the conduct of general tendency and principles that underlies the conduct of states in international affairs. This is so because; foreign policy is a plan and behavior of one state towards another. It deals with internal life and external needs of a

state. But it should be noted that this plan or behavior is a function of geographical, political, historical economical and strategic situation of a state in its bid to maximize its goals aboard. In essence, no state can afford to be indifferent in international affairs. This is true since no state can be completely unaffected by external forces especially in this era.

3. Theoretical Framework

The decision-making theory will be adopted for the purpose of this paper presentation. The proponents of the theory include; Richard Snyder, Burton Sapin, H.W. Bruck and a host of others. The theory focuses on inquiry on actors called 'decision makers' and on the state defined as a 'decisional unit'. The action of the state is seen through the actions of the decision makers (Modelski, 1962) the theory proceeds with the assumption that, the key to political action lies on the way in which decision makers define their situations. This is majorly tied to the internal political events and the positions taken by the various Foreign policy actors, in and outside the state. (Modelski 1962).

The theory also holds that, the setting in which foreign policy decision are made is the one which is perceived appropriate by the decision makers. The setting is conceived as consisting of internal and external parts. The internal setting comprise personalities, decision units, the government and structure within which the decision makers

function, the physical and technological condition of the state, the basic values and goals, and the various influence operating in the society such as religion and ethnic composition; while the external setting includes all relevant factors in the total situation of the international system that exists at a particular period of time (Modelski, 1962).

Hence, the decision-making theory explains foreign policy formulation and implementation in the light of the perception of the decision makers, with regard to all internal and external factors that interplay in the affairs of the state. The approach is found suitable in analyzing the Nigerian situation particularly if one considers the pluralities and complexities that characterized Nigerian Socio-economic history as well as the event that surround the country as at that period of time.

4. Biography of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo

Chief Aremu Mathew Olusegun Obasanjo was born on May 5th 1937 in Abeokuta, Ogun State of Nigerian. He attended a secondary education at the famous Baptist Boys High School, Abeokuta. Though he was unable to attend a university Education, but he was enlisted into the Nigerian Army at the age of 21 where he served in various capacities, including the deputy and later became head of state of the Federal Republic of Nigeria under the military

government between 1975-1979. As they promised, he handed over power to a civilian president, Alhaji Shehu Usman Aliyu Shagari in 1979, and retired at the age of 41 to otta where his farm was established.

Despite his retirement he still had political and economic influence both here at home and outside the country, by bearing in mind on the critical national issues under subsequent military regimes until his arrest and detention in 1996 by Abacha's government but later he was released after the death of General Sani Abacha in 1998 and contested for the presidential election. Consequently he became democratically elected president of Nigeria on the 29th May, 1999 where he served until 2007, though he attempted to amend the constitution in order to allow himself for a third term as president; the proposed amendment was rejected by the senate which left him with no option but to conduct election and handed over power in May 29th, 2007 (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2009).

4.1 Nigerian Foreign Policy under Obasanjo: An Overview

The Nigerian foreign policy under Olusegun Obasanjo seems to be unique in nature. This is because; there were series of frustrating experience which Nigeria had undergone under successive military dictatorship. The situation climaxed under the maximum rule of general Abacha when the country suddenly shrunk into a minuscule

stature. During this period (1993-1998), the external realities of Nigeria became so irritating such that, the country become a pariah within the international system. It was in the thick of this crisis that Abacha died. This paved a way for Abdulsalami Abubakar to become the head of state. On his assumption of office, he took concrete steps to address some of the contending issues, the outcome of which culminated in the return of democracy to Nigeria in 1999 (Jibril, A. 2003).

Domestically, the environment of Nigerian foreign policy since the inception of democracy, has witnessed some transformations. One may recall that, prior to May 29th, 1999, Nigeria had been under the firm grip of military dictatorship for an uninterrupted period of sixteen (16) years. During this period, the domestic realities of Nigeria were not favorably disposed to an effective conduct of foreign policy. But today at least one significant change in the domestic base Nigeria's foreign policy is the fact that Nigeria is now a domestic state. Hence foreign policy decisions can no longer be taken without recourse to the due process of the law. (Jibril, A. 2003).

Moreover, the psychological environment has not remained totally unaltered. Indeed, it has made some tremendous impacts. This perhaps due to the fact that, the key to political action lies in the way, in which decision makers as actors defined their situation and their image of situation is built

around the protected action as well their reason for their action. In this regard, we must appreciate the fact that the foreign policy decision makers in the Nigerian context, have changed. One particular significant is the personality as well as the psychology of the president Obasanjo. It is believed that he brought his credibility, clout and international respectability to an otherwise discredited Nigerian presidency. (Jibril, A. 2003). Thus, it is these changes, which took place at the domestic, external and psychological realms of Nigerian foreign policy that have been crucial to the conduct of Nigerian foreign policy under Obasanjo's democratic regime.

4.2 Foreign Policy Objectives under Obasanjo Administration

On the 29th May, 1999, president Obasanjo in his inaugural speech as the now democratically elected President demonstrated his preparedness to lead Nigeria into new focused foreign policy objectives. In his speech, he emphasized that, his administration shall pursue dynamic foreign policy to promote friendly relation with all nations and will continue to play a constructive role in the United Nation, the African Union and course, other international bodies. (Aliu, 2007).

The importance of this declaration is obvious: first to contemplate friendly diplomatic relations with all nations was to devise a means of addressing the image problems confronting the

country. Secondly, to seek to play a constructive role in U.N. AU and other international bodies was to re-affirm Nigeria's commitment to the principles of multilateralism and Afrocentric (Aliu, 2007). It is against this background, that our appraisal of Nigerian Foreign Policy under Obasanjo's democratic setting would be carried out.

4.3.1 Political Diplomacy

In its determined effort to return Nigeria to the path of global reckoning, Obasanjo's regime opted for a political diplomacy. In this regard the president undertook several foreign trips between the years 1999-2007. According to official sources, the president as at mid-June 2002 was recorded to have visited 113 one hundred and thirteen countries within the years of his administration. (Daily Trust Newspaper July, 2nd 2008) Also in another source, as at August 2002, the president had been out of the country for a period of 340 days (Akindele, 2005). Although, those trips had come under severe criticism, however, their impact on Nigerian foreign policy cannot be easily discarded. However, the approach was able to yield dividends. Not only that the world perception on Nigeria in the international political system changed, there has also been positive reciprocity from great world leaders. For instance, the then British Prime Minister Tony Blair, his Canadian Counterpart, Jean Chretien, the two-former serving United States Presidents, Bill Clinton and his immediate successor, George W. Bush

and President Hu Jin Tao of China among others have all visited Nigeria in the course of Obasanjo's regime. This indeed is a positive development, indicating that Nigeria has been received back into the mainstream of international affairs.

The Obasanjo's administration pursued all its foreign policy objectives with the conscious aim of giving Nigeria a diplomatic face lift among the committee of nation. Since the Obasanjo's idiosyncrasy was more of pro-western, his administration was said to be a messiah because he danced in accordance with whims and caprices which delivered the country from the tribulation within and outside the country. The president began by trying to ease the tension at home and put all domestic variable that was displaced by the previous regimes, however, as he took over power, he started with political and moral fight. Politically, he began to receive those on exile back home, and the release of political detainees arrested by Abacha's regime to faithfully join in the course to build a greater nation. Morally he began by taken measures to reduced poverty in the country. To some extent, this placed the country's image back and gave the citizens of Nigeria some level of respect and confidence.

There is no doubt that President Obasanjo has really succeeded in re-lunching Nigeria into the orbit of international politics. However, it is argued that, the introduction of

democratic rule in Nigeria was indeed a critical success factor which made the world very eager to welcome the country back into fold, in order to perform her natural role as a leader in the West African Sub-Region and indeed Africa.

This indeed manifested when the Obasanjo's administration inherited and successfully implemented the 2003 All African Games Competition tagged COJA games, after the hosting right of FIFA Youths Grade Football Competition was withdrawn at the 11th hour in 1995. Furthermore, Nigeria in a twist history, hosted the Common Wealth Heads of States and Government Meeting (CHOGM) and President Obasanjo subsequently assumed its chairmanship. These were manifest examples of Nigeria's second return to the world scene, a development which has been described as a high point in the foreign policy profile of that administration.

The anti-corruption crusade of the Obasanjo administration has also helped to boost the country's image. The process of which led to the establishment of the Independent Corrupt Practices and other related offences Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC). However, the Commissions were accused of being selective and sentimental.

4.3.2 Economic Diplomacy

Economic diplomacy was one of the policies thrust of the regime which equally witnessed some level of success. The pursuit of economic diplomacy by the regime was multifaceted. These include the struggle for the recovery of funds looted by Abacha and his cronies, the campaign for debt relief as well as the attraction of Direct Foreign Investment (DFI) into the country. The pursuit of looted funds yielded positive result as some of the countries concerned had been in assistance and major parts of the looted funds were recovered into the Nigerian treasury. Though the where about of the funds had generated much controversy as the Obasanjo administration could not provide satisfactory account of the funds. (Daily Independence 20th September, 2005)

Also, the campaign for debt relief yielded substantial result as Nigerian major creditors (e.g Canada, IMF and Paris Club) canceled most of Nigeria's debt. The fact that Canada cancelled \$ 45 million U.S Dollars which Nigeria owed her was remarkable. The President Obasanjo's administration has been described as the hallmark of Nigeria-China relations. Obasanjo's foreign policy on economic growth was majorly inclined towards Asia. Thus, the remark credited to him that "any African country that is keen on economic growth and development should move towards Asia. This philosophy made the administration to make Nigerian

economy assessable to the Asian countries, particularly China and Korea.

During Obasanjo's regime, Nigeria and China signed one of the biggest economic agreements in October 2006. Both countries signed a 25 billion U.S Dollar loan facility, a substantial part which will be used to finance the refurbishment of the Nigerian rail system and the remaining part for the building of Nigeria's communication satellite (NIGCOMSAT). This trend is however, a consolidation of General Abacha's radical shift of Nigeria's foreign policy towards Asia due to the unfavorable stance of the west on his administration (Abati, 2008).

Close to the heart of Obasanjo's foreign policy on economic matters is the African continent. Hence, President Obasanjo was a major player in the formation of New Economic Partnership for African Development (NEPAD) alongside the presidents of Egypt, Senegal, South Africa and Libya. The NEPAD was designed to harmonize the existing African economic relations as well as to explore new ones. President Obasanjo was so committed to the NEPAD project, such that he had to domesticate its principles at National level through the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS). This brought about the overwhelming reforms in the Nigerian Banking Sector and telecommunication enterprise. In the banking industry, the regime went further by creating a standard to banking

system which was termed recapitalization of the banking sector, that for a bank to operate, it must have a minimum capital of ₦25 billion, so as to meet up the global challenges and also contribute to the economic growth and development. While in the telecommunication sector, the GSN was introduced into the economy which invariably ushered in job opportunity to the people.

On the domestic front, Obasanjo's foreign policy on economic relations directly influenced the monetization and privatization of the economy, through the policy of commercialization of some government sectors that were in verge of collapse due to mismanagement by the officials. Though these policies had certain immediate and future harsh impact and therefore attracted criticism from economic analysts. However, the president defends the policies by stating that, they are meant to eradicate the gross wastage and corruption that had characterized the public sector. (Daily Trust, Editorial, February, 3rd 2007).

In addition, the Nigerian Export Promotion Council was set up by the Obasanjo administration to facilitate the bilateral trade agreement entered into by the regime. This has improved Nigerian's exportation capacity by about 7.5%, particularly in the agricultural sector. (Daily Trust, Editorial, February 3rd 2007).

4.3.3 Obasanjo's Foreign Policy on Peace, Security and Conflict Resolution

In his foreign policy objectives towards African continent and commitment to friendly relationship with all countries of the world, the president put effort to make sure that restoration of peace in neighboring African countries had been achieved. For instance, the president has played a leading and significant role in setting the political problem in Sao-Tome and Principe, where the government was overthrown in a coup-de 'tat, when their President was in Abuja attending the civilian summit. Obasanjo became the arrow-head that got the coup plotters to back out and ensured the safe return of the legitimate president. Also, Obasanjo convinced the soldiers that staged a successful military coup in Guinea Bissau to drop their arms and allow the constitutionally elected president continue in office, when he chaired the negotiation meeting which led to the deposed president reclaiming his seat without any bloodshed. (Abati, 2008).

Another major incidence that witnessed the practical experimentation of President Obasanjo's foreign policy on peace and conflict resolution, particularly in Africa was the Darfur Crisis in Sudan Obasanjo's mediation effort reflected his commitment to peace in Africa. The crisis in Darfur began in February 2003, various rebel groups due to alleged neglect and marginalization in the management of not just their own

affairs, but also in the affairs of the entire country, decided to take up arms against the central government in Sudan. The rebel groups are the Sudan People Liberation Movement/Army (SLAM/A) and the Justice and Equity Movement (JEM). The government of Sudan responded by attempting to inflict total military defeat on the rebels. In the process, it allegedly armed the Janjaweed Militia to fight its cause. As a result of the crisis some 100,000 people mostly civilian have been killed, while over one million people have been displaced from homes, some 200,000 of them moved to neighboring Chad. Estimates put the number of people in desperate need of humanitarian aid in the region to over 2 million 2 million. (Daily Trust, July 2nd, 2008).

While the Darfur crisis generated diverse reactions from the world leaders, President Obasanjo state that in his informed judgment and finding, an act of genocide cannot be said to have been perpetrated neither can the crisis be described as a matter of deliberate policy by the government of Sudan. Thus, Obasanjo's position was informed by the comment of U.S Secretary of State, Colin Powell, who described the Darfur crisis as genocide. Hence, Obasanjo did not wait for the outcome of the deliberation of the international community in the Darfur crisis before he swiftly re-lunched and injected greater impetus to the search for peace in the crisis ridden region. (Daily Trust, July 2nd 2008)

However, the seeds that have now germinated in the recent signing of comprehensive peace accord between the government of Sudan and the Sudan People Liberation Movement (SPLM) tied down on those arduous talk facilitated by Nigeria. Indeed, the vexed issues of regional autonomy and the adoption of a quasi-federal structure of government, which recognizes the religious and cultural diversities of the country, were issues that Nigeria's mediation efforts sought to implant in the earring factions and the negotiating teams during the many tears of peace talks. It is gratifying that; these principles have now been accepted as key component of the concluded peace talks that hold better prospects of a lasting peace in Sudan. (This Day Newspaper, April 10th, 2008).

President Obasanjo's foreign policy on conflict management also came to bear in Zimbabwe over the land allocation dispute between British citizen farmers in Zimbabwe and the Zimbabwean government. President Obasanjo mediates in the issue and resolved the problem by bringing the farmers into Kwara State, Nigeria. This gesture gave Nigeria a face lift in conflict management diplomacy as the British government and other international bodies applaud the gesture. (Abati, 2008) Also, the diplomatic way in which President Obasanjo handled the Charles Taylor Saga, further underscores his diplomatic sagacity. He was able to offer him asylum in Nigeria

for peace to reign. Though, President Obasanjo later facilitated Charles Taylor's arrest for his trail of crimes in Sierra Leone. (Abati, 2008).

In regard with international organizations, President Obasanjo supported the campaign for the reform of the United Nations Security Council. He was a fervent apostle of the inclusion of African countries in the Security Council alongside other countries that had been clamoring the course. (Aliu, 2007) At the multilateral level, President Obasanjo made the presence of Nigeria well felt, in attendance of sessions and summits of the United Nations, Common-wealth African Union, ECOWAS, G77, G15, G8, OPEC, World Bank, World Economic Forum UNESCO, Non-Aligned movement and many other organizations and specialized committees (Aliu, 2007).

However, at the bilateral level, President Obasanjo and his counterparts, Abdulaziz Bouteflika of Algeria put together a Bi-National Commission which will see the implantation of three key projects that include the trans-Sahara gas pipeline, the trans-Sahara highway from Lagos to Algeria and the optic fiber link. This Bi-National; Commission (BNS) was the first bilateral economic relationship between Nigeria and Algeria (Daily Trust, Editorial. February, 3rd 2007).

Furthermore, the Nigeria-Mali relationship has blossomed as President Oumar Konare of Mali as ECOWAS

chairman joined forces with president Obasanjo in the Common Interest of Sustaining the spirit ECOWAS. (Daily Trust, Editorial. February 3rd, 2007). The United State and Nigeria have had several diplomatic relationships under Obasanjo administration on the Nigeria-U.S. Joint Economic Committee, Nigeria economic reform and agricultural growth was supported with an increment of United States Agency for International Development (USAID) grant to \$15.6 million U.S Dollars. (Daily Trust, Editorial. February 3rd, 2007).

A further signal of the bilateral relations between Nigeria and the United States is the Military co-operation agreement signed by both countries in the year 2000. The scheme is known as the Military Profession Resources Initiative (M.P.R.I) under the scheme the U.S undertook to send its military institutions and help Nigeria to procure military aid. Under the same arrangement, the U.S government also agreed to assist Nigeria in retraining and re-equipping Nigerian soldiers to enable them perform their peace keeping role more efficiently and effectively (Asobie, 2005) though the Nigeria Military is not happy with the degree of access granted U.S military to Nigeria and feared that it will places the U.S armed forces at an under advantage in any future conflict with Nigeria (Asobie, 2005)

5. Conclusion

Nigeria's foreign policy has since independence been consistently guided by the same principles and objectives. However, the emphasis that has been persistently laid upon them by successive regimes in the country differs depending on the domestic context with which decisions are made, the external environment and the attitudinal posture of the foreign policy makers at a given time. Nigerian foreign policy under Obasanjo's administration had to an extent improved Nigeria's popularity and prestige among the committee of nations. There is no doubt that, the administration succeeded in re-lunching Nigerian into the orbit of international politics her pariah status of the Abacha regime. Probably, the Obasanjo's personal clout, contact and commitment helped a lot in this regard.

However, despite the achievement of the above goals and objectives, the Obasanjo's foreign policy has been unable to effectively harness the vast resources at government disposals to strengthen her domestic economic base, being the core value determinant of country's foreign policy. Evidence has shown that, since the inception of his administration in 1999, there had been recurrent cases of ethnic and religious crises, government instability especially as a result of dishonorable executive-legislative relations, which believed to have a horrifying dimension with the impeachment threat against the president during the first tenure. There

were also election crises, inter and intra party crisis, personality clash, Niger-Delta crises and the number of ethnic militia has also increased across the country.

The most irrational decision ever taken by the administration was the handover, of the oil rich Bakassi peninsular to Cameroon since the territory of the state is one of the components of core values both human and material resources to

defend it. However, in spite of his demonstration both in world and action to make Nigeria regain her image in the eyes of international community, the country's image problems had not been surmounted. This is underscored by the defunct third term agenda and massive rigging exhibited in the 2007 presidential election in which even the succeeding president had to admit that the election was full of irregularities.

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